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Teaching and Tutoring Adult Emergent Readers with Refugee Backgrounds: Implementing a Training Program for Community Volunteers

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the implementation of a two-day training intervention for community volunteer teachers and tutors of adult emergent readers from refugee backgrounds. The volunteer teachers participating in this research typically had no previous training or education in working in literacy education and with adult second language learners. After describing the creation and implementation of the training, the study reports the results of surveys of trainees regarding perceived usefulness of various components of the training. Implications of this data and recommendations for best training practices are discussed, along with recommendations for future research.

INTRODUCTION

Background

It is well-documented in the LESLLA community that adult emergent readers--a population of language learners whose unique needs warrant the attention of highly trained professionals--often lack access to instruction by qualified language teachers (Condelli & Wrigley, 2008; Bigelow & Schwarz, 2010; Burt, Peyton, & Schaezel, 2008). Literature also supports LESLLA teachers' common experience that adult language learners (including emergent readers with refugee or immigrant backgrounds) have limited access to institutional resources when compared to their K-12 or university-level counterparts. Teachers in LESLLA contexts are paid less and are less likely to secure stable, full-time jobs, and as a result, teacher turnover in these contexts is high (Sticht, 2000; Cristoph, 2009; Ross, 1995). In order to address these needs and disparities, programs often rely on the support of volunteer teachers and tutors to teach adult emergent readers. However, without support and training, volunteers may not be able to meet the needs of these learners. Despite these risks, volunteers provide critical support to LESLLA teachers and learners. Effective volunteer training centered on the needs of adult emergent readers with refugee backgrounds is critical for providing volunteers the social and professional support they need to be effective. The following study reports on how LESLLA practitioners collaborated to create and implement such a training.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was 1) to revise and expand a professional development series for instructors and community tutors of ESL adult emergent readers from refugee backgrounds, 2) to understand the impact of this training on participants, and 3) to revise the trainings based on participant feedback. In this research, we aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What do teachers and volunteers learn from participating in a professional development series about working with adult second language learners, specifically L2 adult emergent readers with refugee backgrounds? What information and activities were most helpful, and what do participants wish to learn more about?
2. What observations and reflections do participants have after the professional development series for teachers and volunteers working with adult second language learners, specifically L2 adult emergent readers with refugee backgrounds?
3. How do the observations, reflections, questions, and suggestions that experienced teachers share differ from those that volunteer tutors and classroom assistants share?
4. How can the researchers revise the professional development series according to the articulated needs and reflections of participants to make it more effective?

The results of this study will be of interest to programs in other cities that wish to develop effective volunteer trainings for working with LESLLA learners.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Training opportunities for teachers of LESLLA learners are scarce, and many programs rely on volunteer (rather than professionally trained) teachers who are unlikely to have relevant teaching qualifications (Young-Scholten, Peyton, Sosinski, & Cabeza, 2014). However, training is important because studies show that adult LESLLA learners' language and literacy acquisition accelerates when they are taught by qualified teachers (Condelli, Cronen, Bos, Tseng, & Altuna, 2010, as cited in Young-Scholten, Peyton, Sosinski, & Cabeza, 2014). It is an unfortunate reality that the responsibility for teaching the highest-need LESLLA learners often falls on minimally trained volunteer teachers, rather than highly trained expert teachers who are trained to work with emergent readers.

Research suggests that practical teaching strategies are of greatest interest to LESLLA teachers. According to Young-Scholten, Peyton, Sosinski, and Cabeza (2014), LESLLA practitioners (paid and volunteer) value learning "skills they need to teach effectively" over the "research and knowledge that undergird and support those skills" (p. 165). As such, the training described in this paper focused on "instructional approaches and materials underpinned by research and theory that teachers and managers without specific LESLLA training can use immediately," (p. 177) such as priorities outlined by respondents in Young-Scholten, Peyton, Sosinski and Cabeza's 2014 survey:

- Learning about teaching methods that engaged learners in active participation and built on learners' background knowledge
- Developing and using strategies and materials authentic to students' lived experiences and needs
- Supporting learners in developing reading and writing strategies for independent real-world use
- Implementing lessons that teach oral language skills.

It is important to note that while developing knowledge about methodologies and skills in classroom practice provides a foundation on which to build, it is also recommended that new or volunteer teachers have "opportunities to participate in authentic continuing professional learning activities" (Smith, 2010 as cited in Vinogradov, 2012). Such ongoing support helps LESLLA practitioners "really understand [...] classroom practice and to make wise, informed choices for individual learners" (Vinogradov, 2012). Therefore, trainers of LESLLA practitioners should consider how to address both immediately relevant instructional tools and deep, reflective practice.

Adult learning theory (Knowles, 1984) offers insight into how to create activities that are deeply relevant to adult participants. Knowles positioned the adult learning experience, termed *andragogy*, in opposition to pedagogy. Whereas *pedagogy* is dependent on an instructor who decides what should be learned (content)--the personal experience of the learner is not incorporated and the learner's motivation is expected to be extrinsic--*andragogy* approaches the learning process from a problem-solving perspective. Adult learners are self-directed, have a wealth of experience that informs their worldview, have a readiness to

learn that is contingent on their need to be able to *do* something with that knowledge, and have intrinsic motivation; i.e., searching for a better quality of life, recognition, self-esteem; self-confidence, and self-actualization (Carney, 1986). This theory can be applied to both the volunteers who are being trained, and the refugee-background students they work with.

This literature suggests that including principles of andragogy into trainings is a critical need for LESLLA practitioners, who most value training that involves practical teaching strategies they can incorporate into their own classrooms, i.e., *do* something with the information immediately. Professional community is also important for LESLLA practitioners, who often work in isolation. The curriculum we developed addressed these needs by offering a thorough training about teaching adult emergent readers with refugee backgrounds while also creating a sense of community for participants. In addition, the conceptual framework of adult learning theory underpinned the discussions and activities included in the training as well as the instructional methods taught to participants. In this way, the training aimed to draw upon the participating teachers' experiences and to explicitly demonstrate to them how to do the same for the learners in their classroom.

METHODS

Context

This study took place in a mid-sized city with a large refugee resettlement program in the southwestern United States. This city is a resettlement site for some of the highest-need refugees from around the world. As such, multiple resettlement agencies and non-profit organizations exist to serve adults from refugee backgrounds in formal settings (such as classrooms) and informal settings (such as in apartments where families live). These organizations often enlist the help of paid and volunteer English teachers and tutors who have limited training in best practices (e.g. using oral language as a foundation for beginning literacy; using authentic, age-appropriate materials in the literacy classroom; using a trauma-informed pedagogical approach) for working with adult emergent readers from refugee backgrounds. In 2014, in response to a wave of requests for training, staff at a local literacy and English language acquisition non-profit secured a grant and developed a training to meet this need. The grant enabled the team to develop and offer a training on working with adult English learners with refugee backgrounds, but without further funding, the team was unable to offer ongoing support or additional trainings.

After the 2016 U.S. presidential election, interest in working with refugee-background students in this southwestern U.S. city spiked. Agencies and organizations once again needed help training volunteers interested in teaching English language and literacy to adults from refugee backgrounds. A grassroots organization unaffiliated with established refugee resettlement agencies, and unfamiliar with the programs already available, began providing services, including in-home English classes, prompting the need for volunteer teacher training. In order to address the surge of volunteers, we revised the original 2014 training; the new training focused on best practices in helping adult emergent

readers from refugee backgrounds develop English language oral and literacy skills. The team piloted the revised training with professional instructors of second language adult emergent readers in the spring of 2017 in order to gain insight from professional instructors on what they wanted their volunteers to know, and what they wished they themselves would have known when they first transitioned into an L2 adult emergent readers classroom. The team then revised the pilot and offered its first Community Volunteer Training (CVT1) in the summer of 2017. Though four additional trainings have been offered since then, this paper will focus on the initial two trainings.

Participants

The pilot training was offered in March 2017 to seven participants who were professional educators and managers. Four were experienced instructors in a refugee English program, an English Language Acquisition for Adults (ELAA) and English literacy program that is contextualized around workforce preparation for adults from refugee backgrounds. It is funded by the state refugee resettlement program, and housed in an adult basic education department, which is funded by the Department of Education, of a community college. Other participants included the director of the adult basic education center where we conducted the pilot, the professional learning coordinator for the community college, and one English Language Acquisition for Adults (ELAA) teacher from the adult basic education program. Participating teachers had between 3 and 14 years of teaching experience in this context, and each taught a minimum of eight contact hours per week in a literacy level or low-beginning English Language Acquisition for Adults course.

The first Community Volunteer Training (CVT1) took place in June 2017. On day 1 of the training, there were fourteen participants, and on day 2, there were eleven participants in attendance. The CVT1 participants came from a variety of backgrounds. Unlike participants in the pilot training, most participants in the CVT1 training were not professional teachers, but community volunteers working with learners of refugee backgrounds in homes or classrooms. They were associated with the local non-profit literacy council, church-based organizations, the local refugee resettlement agencies, the grassroots organization that had recently been created and was connecting ESL volunteers to families, and a food security organization that also offers English tutoring as a secondary service.

Data Collection

Curriculum. By piloting the course to experienced teachers first, we hoped to gain input from professional educators before offering the training to community volunteers and tutors.

In order for as many experienced teachers as possible to participate and provide feedback, we gave the pilot training in one, six-hour day though the community trainings were intended to be offered in two, three-hour days. Before lunch, we prepared hands-on activities and discussion to present the following ambitious list of themes: types of L1 literacies, emergent readers, acquisition vs. learning, adult learning theory, cultural indices and doing school, cultural profiles

(including a presentation of resources and problematizing the use of those resources), Affective Filter, Total Physical Response (TPR), and recommendations for using visual aids and graphic devices. Our goal was to raise awareness of each subject and connect key concepts to how they affect practice or why we recommend certain methodologies. After a short break for lunch, we reconvened and discussed assessment, literacy development stages, pre-reading skill development, top-down, bottom up/whole part whole approaches, and the Language Experience Approach (LEA).

Surveys. For the pilot training with the experienced instructors of second language adult emergent readers, we solicited feedback in the form of a five-question survey and group discussion. We asked the participants to dialogically reflect on each activity immediately after we presented it, and we took copious notes on their feedback. We distributed the open-ended surveys at the beginning of the session, asking them to complete the surveys throughout the training and to submit them at the end. The surveys included questions about what participants wanted to learn and practical and theoretical tools they hoped volunteers working in their classrooms could learn from a training. A full list of questions for the pilot study is included in Appendix A.

For the Community Volunteer Training (CVT1), we collected data in the form of anonymous pre-session and post-session surveys administered at the beginning and end of each training day. The surveys ranged in length from 5 to 11 questions and consisted of both Likert scales and open-ended free response. Likert scale questions asked participants to rate the usefulness of various activities and their comfort knowing where to start and how to develop lessons for adult emergent readers with refugee backgrounds, and open-ended questions inquired about participants' experiences and needs, and how they defined *literacy* and *emergent readers*. The surveys asked repeated questions as a means of gauging the participant's learning and the training's efficacy. A full list of questions for the pre- and post-surveys for each day of the CVT1 is included in Appendix B. The data from the experienced instructors' pilot training was analyzed by theme. The data from the CVT1 responses were analyzed thematically as well as quantitatively using the statistical program R (R core team, 2013).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Qualitative Findings: Participant Feedback from the Pilot Training

During the pilot session, teachers provided valuable feedback in the reflective dialogue and on the open-ended surveys. Among their comments, they suggested addressing culture alongside literacy, and not as a separate theme or afterthought. They recommended explaining the impact of cultural etiquette (such as leave-taking rituals) on how students are received inside and outside of the classroom. They pointed out that this issue is important for tutors as well as learners. The teachers also recommended emphasizing how respect is manifested in the classroom. They reported that some community volunteers, though well-intentioned, had disrespected their students in disturbing ways, including by talking about their vacation in a country a learner had fled, indicating surprise about learners' home situations (for example, the number of children they had),

and touching their headscarves. The teachers recommended being explicit about how tutors can show respect for students, their life experiences, and circumstances, and about how to create an asset-based, not deficit-based, learning environment. To this end, they suggested training through anecdotes so volunteers could consider the impact of behaviors on learners, and teaching volunteers how to consider students' lives beyond the classroom (such as their home and community resources, technology use, etc.). Finally, the teachers reminded us that we should consider the expectations we had for paid staff vs. volunteers and focus mainly on themes related to tutoring or helping in a classroom, not necessarily teaching a lesson. To this end, they reported that it would be helpful to incorporate practical advice over theory, and recommended addressing how to use teachable moments in the classroom, demonstrating how to search for visuals, and presenting questioning strategies to promote awareness of how to use accessible language to communicate with learners.

Revisions to the Pilot Training

We revised the pilot training by incorporating the experienced teachers' feedback. This revision would be presented to our Community Volunteer Training 1 (CVT1) cohort. See Appendix C for the training agenda we used with CVT1. First, we eliminated most theoretical content in favor of concrete and immediately relevant information and strategies. We also included a variety of experiential activities; for example, we started the training with "mediocre" and "great" lesson demonstrations in Spanish in order to help participants understand how it felt to be a beginning language learner, as well as to demonstrate the effectiveness of activities like TPR, visuals, repetition, and deliberate teacher talk at the beginning levels of language learning. In addition, we included an activity in which participants were shown a sign for a hospital in Arabic and asked to quickly copy it down. We hoped this activity would demonstrate how it feels to not be able to read important information in a different script, as well as lead into a discussion of language practice in context. Furthermore, in order to demonstrate the importance of context and background knowledge, we asked participants to read a brochure in Somali with and without the context of headers and pictures; this demonstrated both bottom-up and top-down approaches, and provided a venue to discuss the importance of each approach. On the first day, we added a hands-on, multimodal vocabulary lesson, which we simultaneously demonstrated while explaining why and how we were incorporating strategies we had discussed in the training; finally, on the second day, we did a Language Experience Approach (LEA) lesson with the class, where we asked them to generate the text and we gave them suggestions for extension activities and integration of whole language with phonics.

To discuss culture, we included role plays about intercultural communication. These role plays were subversively inserted into the midst of the training content; for example, while one trainer was leading a discussion about levels of literacy, another trainer loudly entered the room and began greeting all the participants. The first trainer modeled how to deal with the interrupting "student," finished the discussion, and then brought the participants' awareness

back to the disruptive act, asking “Why do you think that happened? How did you notice I dealt with it? Why was it successful?”

In order to address stages of literacy development without lecturing or without use of excessive academic jargon, we showed examples of child and adult work, discussed the differences and similarities, and asked participants to order another set of literacy development examples. We retained the discussion about what makes an adult emergent reader “emergent” so that we could focus on strengths instead of deficits, and specified that we were including such terminology so that our participants would be well-informed, and know what search terms to use when looking on the internet or in the library for more information. We also kept the lecture about the types of literacies and the difference between *learning* and *acquisition*. After the session, we e-mailed participants a practical toolkit which included information about where to learn more, as well as teaching resources. The next stage in this study investigates how community volunteers responded to this revised training.

Community Volunteer Training (CVT1): Quantitative Survey Results

After revising the pilot training, we offered the first Community Volunteer Training (CVT1) in June 2017 at a local non-profit which offers free ESL classes at public schools, libraries, and churches in the community. We offered this training in two, three-hour sessions.

Before and after the first session, and at the end of the second session, we asked participants to provide feedback in the form of a brief survey in which we asked participants to use a 1-5 Likert scale to rate their comfort level knowing where to start with language learners (Figure 1) and knowing how to develop lesson plans (Figure 2). In addition, we asked them to rate the usefulness of seven elements of the training: 1) explanations of terminology/research, 2) literacy simulations (Arabic sign and Somali brochure), 3) role plays, 4) group work and discussions, 5) discussion of visual aids, 6) the toolkit, which is a Google drive folder that includes articles on practice and methodology, resources on research, links to videos, other local learning opportunities, and works cited, and 7) lesson demonstrations (Figure 3).

As Figures 1 and 2 indicate, participants report much greater comfort after the end of the first session (from 3.18 to 4.00 on “knowing where to start,” and from 2.75 to 3.75 on a 5-point Likert scale on “developing lessons for language/literacy learners”). Their comfort level increases even more by the end of the second three-hour session (to 4.32 and 4.23, respectively).

Participants’ self-reported comfort knowing where to start and their comfort developing lessons were analyzed in the statistical software R (R core team, 2013) using a two-factor within-subjects ANOVA, with time (pre, mid, and post) and answer as the factors. Results indicate that time was significant overall ($F(2,62)=33.9, p<.0001$), with participants reporting higher comfort levels at the end of the training than at the beginning. This was true for both questions. Follow up pairwise comparisons tests were conducted to determine if participants’ gains were significant at each level of time. Results indicated that participants reported increased comfort from the beginning to end of day 1 ($F(1,41)=27.4, p<.0005$), as well as from the end of day 1 to the end of day 2

($F(1,35)=10.45, p<.003$). These results indicate that participants' comfort level knowing where to start and planning lessons increased significantly after each day of training.

Figure 1: CVT1 Participant comfort knowing where to start before, during, and after training

Figure 2: CVT1 Participant comfort developing lessons before, during, and after training

As the survey results indicate, participants indicated that the training was too academic and too classroom-based, with not enough emphasis on one-on-one or small group teaching contexts. As Figure 3 illustrates, they also found the academic terminology and literacy simulations slightly less useful than activities such as modeling visual aids, the toolkit, and lesson demonstrations. For us as the researchers and trainers, this means that we need to be more explicit on the importance of the academic terminology and how participants can *use* it in their practice. For example, the participants can more accurately look up further

information on topics discussed in the training, and, by using the academic terms, better ensure they are accessing current best practices in the field. We also need to more explicitly discuss the salience of the literacy simulations. For example, many of the participants noted that they felt uncomfortable during the literacy simulations; as trainers, it was our intent to make our participants feel as uncomfortable as our students might feel in new and culturally different educational environments. Therefore, a more detailed debriefing of those training elements is needed.

Figure 3: CVT1 Participant ranking of usefulness of training elements

In the verbal feedback that they gave, participants stated that full lesson demonstrations were very beneficial—particularly the accompanying discussion and demonstration of the scaffolding teachers build into their lessons to prepare their students for future activities. They also appreciated the discussion of how to choose and use appropriate visual aids, and the concrete demonstration of effective visual aids and visual aids that do not provide enough context or 3D space to be useful in initially introducing new vocabulary.

Finally, participants noted the power of personal experience from refugee-background students, as one refugee-background volunteer attended CVT1 and provided numerous examples from his home culture, as well as learning and educational experiences.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In response to this feedback from CVT1, we decided to revise future Community Volunteer Trainings to make them accessible to individuals with no teaching background, provide ample time for sharing and discussion, and shift from explanatory to participatory activities. We decided to add a glossary of the academic terms used in the training to the shared digital toolkit in order to provide a concrete reiteration of the usefulness of certain academic terms. Our hope was that participants would then use these terms when searching for resources. In addition, we realized that we needed to address culture explicitly, as our attempts to integrate examples with other activities only confused participants (for example, when we picked our noses, pointed with our middle fingers, and invaded our participants' personal space, participants remained decidedly unreactive, yet acknowledged being uncomfortable in the surveys). In addition, we realized that we should expand the amount of time allotted for the

discussion of culture. Participants were most conversational during the educational culture section; however, because we had allotted only a brief period of time for this discussion, we had to move on before participants were finished reflecting. Furthermore, it became apparent during CVT1 that we needed to include a brief discussion of how to address trauma in the classroom. For example, many of our participants asked us how they could ask their students about their past traumatic experiences. Though participants wanted to be helpful, directly asking about trauma is culturally insensitive and potentially retraumatizing, and volunteers who bring up trauma can unintentionally trigger those who have experienced it. In order to help participants understand, we responded by asking participants to consider how it might feel if an acquaintance or stranger asked about one of the most difficult times in their lives. In addition, we likened asking adults with refugee backgrounds about trauma to the cultural faux pas in the United States of asking a veteran about their service in direct combat.

Another critical aspect of the training was including trainers with refugee backgrounds. We agreed to be deliberate about inviting former students to join the training team for future trainings. Finally, we decided to be very intentional so that our language, PowerPoint images, and scenarios explicitly included in-home volunteers as well as classroom volunteers.

Implications

Based on feedback from CVT1 participants, the training team advocates a number of best practices for trainings of community volunteers. First and foremost, the training should be as accessible and practical as possible. It should include “the least you should know” and “where to go to learn more” (Henrichsen, 2010). In general, involving participants in hands-on demonstrations of lesson activities was more effective than simply explaining the activities. Most of our participants had no teaching background and were confused by our use of academic terminology. As such, the training team recommends carefully and explicitly choosing any academic terminology used; for example, we strayed away from using terms like *power distance index* when discussing culture, but continued to include terms like *adult emergent reader*. We recommend telling participants that the target academic terminology is being included so that when participants are looking for resources independently, they can find high quality materials by using appropriate search terms. Sharing a glossary is also recommended.

Secondly, we recommend limiting the number of examples given to illustrate categories or phases. For example, when discussing types of literacies (preliterate, non-literate, semi-literate, non-Roman alphabet literate), one rich example should be given for each, but not a list of short examples for each. We found that though we as LESLLA professionals were interested in talking about the differences between given languages and literacies, the participants were unsure of the direct application of this section, as demonstrated by responses on the post-training evaluations. This type of additional information can be included in a Resource Toolkit shared with participants after the training. We recommend devoting ample time to discussions of cross-cultural communication, particularly

as it manifests in formal and informal educational settings. Discussions of cross-cultural scenarios are particularly helpful as participants are able to see themselves in the situation, and thus reflect more deeply. In order to address the variety of settings in which volunteers work, training content and materials should reference both classroom and in-home settings. Finally, the team recommends including ample time for participants to process training content in individual reflection and pair or group conversation.

Limitations and Future Research

Future research will look at the results of two training interventions provided for university students and professors on a university campus and will include suggestions on modifying training content for an academic or pre-service audience. Additional future research will consider the impact of the changes made to the CVT1 session in subsequent Community Volunteer Training sessions. We have provided and revised two CVTs and two trainings on a university campus since conducting the research presented here. Results of the research conducted on subsequent CVTs will be shared in future presentations.

Limitations of the study include the small sample size of participants, and the possibility that the results are not generalizable to trainees of different educational backgrounds and more extensive teaching experience. The pilot training also consisted of a small group of professional educators; additional professional instructors would have yielded more generalizable suggestions.

While one-shot workshops allow for surface-level introductions to topics and strategies, research shows that continuing education opportunities of longer duration are more effective (Desimone, 2009; as cited in Vinogradov, 2013) because they give teachers time and opportunities to “interact with colleagues and to reflect on their classrooms and research findings” (Burt, Peyton, Schaezel, 2008; Vinogradov, 2012b as cited in Vinogradov, 2013). As such, future research needs to include longitudinal assessments and evaluations, as well as suggestions on incentivizing follow-up meetings with participants.

This article described how a six-hour training was developed and implemented with teachers and tutors working with adult emergent readers in a variety of contexts, including community-based volunteer settings. This information will be valuable for other programs or professionals seeking to develop a similar volunteer training in their own cities or contexts.

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APPENDIX A: QUESTIONS FOR EXPERIENCED LESLLA TEACHERS

Pilot Survey Questions:

1. What did you wish you knew before you started teaching? What do you think would have been too abstract before you actually got in the classroom?
2. What do you want to know about working with volunteers?
3. What parts of this training should tutors have before they set foot in the classroom or work with students one-on-one and what parts should they have after have some experience?
4. What do you want to know more about in depth in the future?
5. What type of activities or examples can you think of to demonstrate specific concepts? What ideas do you have for hands-on parts of the training? What examples do you have from your classroom experience to illustrate particular concepts or aspects?

APPENDIX B: PRE- AND POST-SURVEY QUESTIONS FOR DAYS 1 AND 2 OF COMMUNITY VOLUNTEER TRAINING 1 (CVT1)

CVT Pre-Day 1 Survey:

1. On a scale one to five, how comfortable are you with knowing where to start with teaching/tutoring language learners?
(not comfortable) 1 2 3 4 5 (very comfortable)
2. On a scale of one to five, how comfortable are you with developing lessons for language/literacy learners?
(not comfortable) 1 2 3 4 5 (very comfortable)
3. What techniques would you like to learn for teaching listening and speaking?
4. What listening and speaking strategies do you currently employ in your classes/sessions with your students?
5. What is an adult emergent reader?
6. What do you wish you knew about your students?
7. How do you use visual aids in your sessions?

CVT Post-Day 1 Survey:

1. On a scale one to five, how comfortable are you with knowing where to start with language learners?
(not comfortable) 1 2 3 4 5 (very comfortable)
2. On a scale of one to five, how comfortable are you with developing lessons for language/literacy learners?
(not comfortable) 1 2 3 4 5 (very comfortable)
3. What are best practices for selecting visual aids for use in class?
4. What elements of the training were most useful to you?
5. Which elements do you wish to explore in more detail?

CVT Pre-Day 2 Survey:

1. What techniques would you like to learn for teaching reading, and writing?
2. What strategies do you currently employ in your classes/sessions with your students?
3. What is literacy?
4. What are some best practices for teaching reading and writing with adult emergent readers?
5. When should you introduce print literacy into your lessons?

CVT Post-Day 2 Survey:

1. What elements of the training were most useful to you? Please rate each element (1 = not useful, 5 = very useful)
 - Role Plays
 - Toolkit
 - Explanations of Terminology and Research
 - Visual Aids (e.g. powerpoint, modeling)
 - Lesson Walk-through (e.g. fruit lesson, Spanish lessons, LEA)
 - Literacy Simulation (e.g. Arabic sign and Somali brochure)
 - Groupwork/Discussions

Other (please write in)

Please write additional comments that you may wish to leave about these elements:

2. After the training, on a scale one to five, how comfortable are you with knowing where to start with language learners?
(not comfortable) 1 2 3 4 5 (very comfortable)
3. After the training, on a scale of one to five, how comfortable are you with developing lessons for language/literacy learners?
(not comfortable) 1 2 3 4 5 (very comfortable)
4. Which teaching techniques do you wish to explore in more detail?
5. What is literacy?
6. What is an adult emergent reader?
7. What are some best practices for teaching reading and writing with adult emergent readers?
8. When should you introduce print literacy into your lessons?
9. What did you learn about using visual aids?
10. How do you learn about your students' backgrounds?
11. What did you learn about addressing cultural differences in class/teaching situations?

APPENDIX C: DAYS 1 AND 2 TRAINING AGENDAS FOR COMMUNITY VOLUNTEER TRAINING 1 (CVT1)

Day 1 Training Agenda

Gallery Walk with Flipcharts (Gauging participants' prior knowledge)

Gallery Walk with Flipcharts (Gauging participants' prior knowledge)

Opening and Framing the Training

Participant Introductions

Mediocre Class and Great Class Simulation (in Spanish)

“Doing School”

Different types of education

Assets and challenges to learning

Goals for learning

Stretch Break

Literacy/Literacies

Types of literacies

Definitions of literacy

Uses of literacy

Authentic Literacy Use Exercise (Arabic sign copying)

Summary of Literacy

Stretch Break

Authentic Opportunities for Practicing Language (Meet and greet role play)

Building the Foundation: Receptive and Oral Language Development

Total Physical Response

Visual Aids

Levels of Questioning

Developing Vocabulary and Language Structures

Day 1 End

Summarize the day

Ask evaluation questions

Discuss homework

Day 2 Training Agenda

Opening

Review of Day 1

Discussion of respect for students' past experiences

Framing for Day 2 – Participants' Experiences Working with Literacy Learners

Discussion of Day 1's Homework

Think/Pair/Share – Acquisition vs. Learning Re: Children's Language and Literacy

How do children learn language?

How do children learn to read?

Adult Literacy Acquisition vs. Childhood Literacy Acquisition

Literacy Acquisition Exercise

Assessing Reading and Writing Readiness

Increasing Print Awareness and Developing Pre-Reading Skills

Stretch Break

Approaches to Literacy Instruction*Bottom-up Approach (Somali text)**Top-down Approach (Somali text)**Whole-Part-Whole***Language Experience Approach/Using Meaningful Texts****Language Experience Approach Practice****Share Resource Toolkit****Day 2 End***Summarize the day**Ask evaluation questions**Discuss next steps*